

Notebook 4

The group must create a story that includes human or non-human actors that are part of the sociotechnical ecosystem for the speculated date. The narrative should address how the introduced technology minimizes negative impacts and enhances positive impacts, highlighting its benefits and technological innovation.

1. Identification of Actors:

Include human and non-human characters that interact within the future sociotechnical ecosystem. Some of these actors may have been mapped in the “sociotechnical board,” while new actors may have emerged.

2. Relationship between Actors and Technology:

Describe how the different actors use the speculated solution in the future. What are the relationships between the actors and the artifact, and how are these interactions and relationships constructed?

3. Narrative Development:

Choose one actor (human or non-human) and develop the narrative from their point of view. This actor will serve as the guiding thread of the story.

Give names to the characters to make the story more engaging and realistic.

Specify the time period in which the story takes place, in accordance with the previously speculated scenario. Describe the setting of this period, including social, economic, and environmental aspects.

Group:

Perspective of which author?

Activity Flow

Space reserved for the Future Narrative from the point of view of the actor (human or non-human)

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Group:

Perspective of which author?

Activity Flow

